

A STUDY OF THE *RAJADHAMMASANGAHA* AND DEMOCRACY

Khin Hnin Lwin*

Abstract

This paper is an attempt to point out how the *Rajadhammasangaha* is related to the Myanmar political thought written by U Bo Hlaing, the Yaw Atwinwun in the reign of King Thibaw under the Konbaung Dynasty and why it is the forerunner of democratic government system in Myanmar. The problem is, "How and why the *Rajadhammasangaha* reveals the democratic elements in governmental system?"¹ The tentative solution is that the *Rajadhammasangaha* reflects Myanmar ethical and cultural values. It is based on the seven rules of *aparihaniya* held by the Licchavi princes in the life-time of Lord Buddha and the princes could peacefully govern their country and people those whose are safeguarded in a long period of years by their ruling system, which is founded on democracy peacefully govern.² The research methods of this paper are descriptive and evaluative methods.³ The research principle is comparative.⁴ This paper points out that it is Myanmar own political thought based on the eastern origin and that *Rajadhammasangaha* paves the way of future development of democracy in Myanmar.⁵

Keywords: The Seven Rules of *Aparihaniya*, Democracy, the *Rajadhammasangaha*

Introduction

The *Rajadhammasangaha* is about Myanmar political thought written by U Bo Hlaing, the Yaw Atwinwun in the reign of King Thibaw under the Konbaung Dynasty. Though Thibaw became a king, he had only Buddhist religious knowledge and no experiences in ruling the country and politics. U Bo Hlaing wrote *Rajadhammasangaha* to give lessons and guidelines the new young king for the sake of governing the country well. It is mostly in line with democratic practices which are for all levels governmental system. Moreover, it is based on Myanmar cultural and ethical values, Myanmar traditional theory of *Mahasammamata* in *Manu Dhammathad* and *hiri-ottapa*. Particularly, the emphasis on the seven rules of *aparihaniya*, ten rules for royal behavior, and four rules of sangha is made in order to make good governance and peace society.

Though the *Rajadhammasangaha* is based on **the seven rules of *aparihaniya*** held by the **Licchavi** princes in the life-time of the Buddha, the Yaw Atwinwun emphasizes only three elements among them such as (1) Consultation in a body (conference for exchange of information and advice) (2) Acting by consensus (3) Behaviour in accordance with the law.

In the introduction of the *Rajadhammasangaha*, the minister Yaw Atwinwun openly revealed his own ideology about politics. In ruling the country, if it is ruled by the authorities of one or two persons it may commits the fallacies because the ruling persons are not perfect due to human nature. Therefore, that kind of ruling system of one or two persons should not be

* Lecturer, Department of Philosophy, Dagon University

¹ Research Problem

² Tentative Solution

³ Research Methods

⁴ Research Principle

⁵ Contribution

performed, but the system of consultation or conference in a body for the discussion and exchange information should be held.

Besides, U Bo Hlaing added his own political ideas that the country should be governed with laws as well as with laws in distributing the treasure for royal families. The minister attempted to restrict the king's powers by the requests of the ministers and people. That kind of restriction had been applied in England; it is called charter of Magna Carta which restricts the king's power by the people.

But, the attempt of minister was not successful. He was lower down his status and ranks as a punishment after that *Rajadhammasangha* had been written within 50 days.

In his *Rajadhammasangha*, the minister added the Myanmar traditional theory of *Maharsammata Min* in *Manu dhammathad*, which describes the social contract theory between king and the people. Besides, the minister enclosed the important role of ethical doctrine of *hiri-ottappa* and **ten rules for royal behaviors** for a king in governing the country, and that of the four rules of *sangaha* in his doctrine.

The minister was often lower down his status due to his brave challenges to the old and out of date traditional conceptions of Myanmar kings held by both King Mindon and King Thibaw. But, dramatically he had saved the crisis that country treasure was going to fall down into the hands of France. That undesirable event had happened that the minister Kinwun Mingyi had made treaty with the France to permit the use of Mogoke land of gems during his embassy visit to the France. But, King Mindon did not agree that matter. But in accordance with the treaty, when the French representatives reached the Myanmar palace, the Yaw Atwinwun leader of Myanmar ministers showed the Myanmar's worthy Nga Mauk Rubby to the French representatives, and asked them to decide its value. The French could not be able to value it. On account of it, the Myanmar king could abolish the treaty of permitting the use of Mogoke land arguing that "if one of the rubies in Myanmar could not be able to value how it would be possible to evaluate many gems of that kind in the Moogoke land.

However, it may acknowledge that the Yaw Atwinwun has courage to tell the truths and he had revolutionary mind-set though his mind-set and courage had sent him often down falls of status in his life. But, the Yaw Atwinwun had decided that he will exchange his status for the benefits of country and people. Thus, his famous Myanmar political thought should be studied in completeness as follows:

The Seven Rules of *Aparihaniya*

Aparihaniya means dhamma that cannot be diminished or destroyed and it also means the rules of progress. It can be regarded that the Seven Rules of *Aparihaniya* render the well-being of a kingdom. As long as those rules are kept by the government and people, that country cannot be diminished but be increased. These seven rules are as follows:

1. Consultation in a body (conference for exchange of informations and advices)

The Licchavi Princes and the Vesali people meet together as needed and for so long as may be needed. They will meet and consult for long hours if necessary. So long as time is devoted to meeting and consultation, the well-being of the Licchavi princes and that of the Vesali people will increase. This is to be desired and this is a kind of stabile rule.

2. **Acting by consensus**

The Licchavi Princes at their meeting will always come to an agreement. They will rise up from their councils in agreement on what action is to be taken in the Vesali country. For all such time as they act in agreement, the well-being of the Licchavi Princes will increase. This is to be desired; this will not be diminished. This is one rule of stability.

3. **Behaviour in accordance with the law**

The Licchavi Princes will not decide upon the issue of an order unless the Vesali people have consented to the law before it is made; they will not change a law that is made with this consent. They will consider what laws will be required to be made in the Vesali country before the need arises and behave accordingly. For all the time during which they follow such agreed law, the well-being of Licchavi Princes and that of the Vesali people will increase. This is to be desired; this will not be diminished. This is one rule of stability.

4. **Respect for the admonishments of superiors**

At all times the Licchavi Princes will act with respect towards whatever old people there may be among the Vesali people. They will regard them as important. They will treat them with respect and love. They will honour them and remember to listen to their words. For all such time as they act thus, the well-being of the Licchavi Princes and that of the Vesali people will increase. This is to be desired; this will not be diminished. This is one rule of stability.

5. **No oppression of women**

The Licchavi Princes will not abduct or wrong the wives or daughters of the Vesali people. They will not force them to pass their lives in the houses of the rulers. For all such time as they act thus, the well-being of the Licchavi Princes and that of the Vesali people will increase. This is one rule of stability.

6. **Respecting the rites of the spirit guardians of the towns and villages**

The Licchavi Princes will at all time render honour to whatever guardian spirits there may be, both within and without the cities of the Vesali people. They will make offerings to them and they will in no way reduce the food offerings and the drink offerings that have been customary in the past, save for the taking of life. For all such time as they act thus, the well-being of the Licchavi Princes and that of the Vesali people will increase. This is to be desired; this will not be diminished. This is one rule of stability.

7. **Protection for the monkhood**

The Licchavi Princes will see that good provision is made for the **arahats** who are honoured in the Vesali country and for other **arahats**, who have not yet visited their lands. They will consider in their hearts how these may carry out their religious duties in peace and how they should be guarded so that they may be secure in accordance with the Law. For all such time as they act thus, the well-being of the Licchavi Princes and that of the Vesali people will increase. This is to be desired; this will not be diminished. This is one rule of stability.

Thus, the meaning of the "*aparithaniya*" is "what cannot be diminished or destroyed". It can be said therefore that the rules of *aparithaniya* are the rules of progress. Among these elements of progress, (1) **Consultation in a body** which is called *sannipata*, (2) Acting by consensus or the rule of the assembly which is called *samagga* and (3) enactment of laws which is called *Panyatta*. Those elements are essential parts of Democracy.

U Bo Hlaing added political ideologies in the *Rajadhammasangha*

In his *Rajadhammasangha*, the minister added (1) the power of a general assembly, (2) the Myanmar traditional theory of *Mahasammata Min* in *Manu dhammathad*, which describes the social contract theory between king and the people, (3) the ethical doctrine of *hiri-ottappa* which is very important for a king in governing the country; and (4) the four rules of *sangaha*.

(1) The Power of general assembly

If the ruling power of government is in the hands of only one or two of overwhelming influence, and people have no power it will be ruined. No one or two individual persons have perfect knowledge. Thus, only general agreement which is the product of mutual discussion of assembly can bring forth the fairness and justice. It is only by governing in this way that the country will advance and prosper.

In the same way, even when a king and his officials meet together in council, it is only from their agreement that advantage is derived. If they fail to agree, there is no benefit. However many people compose the assembly, if they fail to reach agreement, the assembly will fall apart. Holding the meeting at the given time and place

1. Setting the time for the adjournment
2. Setting the intended agenda and arranging for an opportunity of speaking for everyone who wishes to speak. Thus it will be possible to reach agreement on the best course.
3. Making an effort to ensure that when action is to be taken, it is with the general consent and that there is no secrecy. Only when agreement is reached in this way, the wealth of country will increase without a downturn. That way is called *Samagga* (harmony).

(2) The Myanmar traditional theory of *Mahasammata Min* in *Manu dhammathad*

According to that theory, in the beginning of the world, before the elevation of *Mahasammata* to be king, when people dispute among themselves, there was no one to resolve the problem. They said to him, "if you agree to guide us and adjudicate in our disputes, we will give you for your sustenance (nourishment) as much as we gain ourselves from our own commerce so that you need not concern yourself with working in the fields or at trade". That chieftain required to guard the country, accepted the proposal and was elected to the kingship. Since he had been chosen by the body of the people to be king, he became known as King *Mahasammata*.

(3) The important role of *hiri-ottappa*

The Yaw Atwinwun, U Bo Hlaing encloses the principles that sustain the world (*lokapala taya*). According to this principle, there are two guarding principles that save the world from destruction. They are *hiri* (shame) and *ottappa* (fear). These two principles sustain and nurture the world. In truth, if these two principles did not exist, our societies will destroy and there will not be moral principles. If a person has no morality he is an animal. For a king in ruling the citizens he must keep the moralities that a king ought to keep.

(4) The four rules of *sangaha*

The four of *sangaha* praise the advancement of whole kingdom. They are

1. *Sassamedha*
2. *Purisamedha*
3. *Sammapasa*
4. *Vacapeyya*

Those who carry on the work of government, kings who are masters of states, follow these principles in recognizing and promoting those who guard the welfare of the lands which they rule.

1. *Sassamedha*

In this world a country may be rich and happy, but it may be invaded and destroyed by a neighbor. It can also be attacked and destroyed from within by its own criminals and thieves. In such a state of insecurity, merchants will be unable to carry on their trade properly. Country people too will not be able to work well. Support for their trade and agriculture will keep them from interruption and it is right that support and protection should be given to these activities in cooperation with the country's rulers.

2. *Purisamedha*

It is not right that after this tax money has been collected for providing support for the country's traders and cultivators, it should not be handed out at will in other affairs. Tax money that has been collected for protecting trade and agriculture must be spent only for the maintenance and expenses of the government servants and military who have the duty of protecting traders and farmers from danger.

3. *Sammapasa*

If there is an intention to advance the country, or to dominate another country, this can be done by collecting a strong military force. In order to provide a strong military force, tax collections are called for. To increase the tax collections, help must be given to country people and traders and they must be encouraged to increase their productivity.

4. *Vacapeyya*

The world's rule is that people only like to hear themselves addressed in pleasant and friendly fashion. This is not true only of people, it applies to the animal world too. Because rough speech causes demerit and evil and must be avoided, pleasant speech is not only advantageous in this world, but in the next it provides a good passage to the world of the spirits. Such pleasant speech constitutes *Vacapeyya*.

Since the minister had added above his own political ideas in addition to the thoughts of the seven rules of *aparhaniya* of the Licchavi Princes in his *Rajadhammasangha*, it is now important to compare the elements of *Rajadhammasangha* with the characteristics of democracy defined by world political philosophers. The following are the general characteristics of democracy, and its origin and development to measure with it.

Ten Rules for Royal Behaviors

1. Dana (giving)
2. Sila (all religious duties are maintained in public practice)
3. Paricchaga (support is provided beyond the religious obligation)
4. Ajjiava (the king is upright, speaking without deception)
5. Maddhava (a disposition to act gently and kindly with good intentions)
6. Tapa (an internal religious life)
7. Okodha (the king is always ready to restrain his anger)
8. Avihimsa (a spirit of compassion towards the common people)
9. Khanti (forgiveness of the actions)
10. Aviroddhana (the king must never antagonize his people). The last of royal conduct is very important for relation to rulers and people. If a ruler opposes his own people, they

will bring down that ruler. This idea is akin to the notion of Locke's right of revolution. The right of revolution cannot assess the value of democratic right for people.

Meaning of Democracy, its origin and historical development

Meaning of Democracy

The simplest meaning of democracy is "People's ruling power". In a literal sense, "Democracy" means government by the people. The word "Democracy" originated in two Greek words, *demos*, meaning "the people" and *kratia*, meaning "rule". American President, Jefferson defined its meaning as, "Democracy is the government of the people, by the people for the people". Democracy is the ruling system in which people possess the authority. The concept of "Democracy" implies majority rule, minority and individual rights, equality of opportunity, equality under the law, and civil rights and liberties in the modern era. All successful modern democracies have incorporated constitutional guarantees of individual rights and such structural safeguards as separation of power, judicial review and other checks and balances.

In state power, major organs are divided into three: legislative, judicial, and administrative organs. In the democracy countries, in order to be fair and justice, the three organs are separated. Thus they can be performed by check and balance theory. Among those three powers, the legislative power is most important and that power is possessed by the peoples' representative general assembly.

Origin of Democracy and its historical development

The occurrence of democratic ruling system is not a deliberate attempt but it had emerged by the determination of social and political necessities in human history. It can be studied as follows.

In ancient history of politics, the ruling system began with **chieftain of kinship**. The people elected their chieftain of group to rule in order to get peace and security. But, when it took long time, the positions of head of the groups were inherited, and it led to **the monarchy**. And then it reached to the stage of **absolute monarchy**.

The first monarchs were honest and kept the moralities which were deserved to keep for a king. But, later monarchs were cruel, and they had no moralities to be kept. Thus, the people and the aristocrats took unity and agreement; they abolished the cruel kings and established **aristocracy**. At first the aristocratic governments were good and could manage for people's prosperities and well beings. But, later on the pure form of aristocracy became corrupt form of **oligarchy**, which was formed not with intelligent persons but the wealthy men.

Because of their cruelty, the tyrants appeared and they captured the ruling power and established **tyranny** in human history. In tyranny, some tyrants were good and they could create the opportunities and prosperities for the people but the most tyrants were very cruel. Their cruelties were the worst.

So, people began to reconsider their past history that they gave the ruling power to the kings, at first the kings were good and took the security and welfares for the people. But, later on they became evil. Then, people constructed the aristocracy, but they also had bad characters later on. Thus, the tyranny had been built up but they were crueller than the former systems.

So, people did not believe any systems before, and they did not want to hand over the ruling power to the others. People did not trust anyone, and they decided to hold the ruling power themselves. Thus, people's ruling power had reached into the hands of the people by the necessity of history.

Different development of Democracy Systems

It has saying, "Athens had born Democracy". In Athens of the Greece, **direct democracy** had developed. In its system, all the adult citizens had to attend the general assembly which was held 10 times in a year. That general assembly decided the laws of Athens. Under it, there was a council of 500 which operated the decisions laid down by the general assembly. And there were many local courts in which every citizen had to serve as jury daily.

In the age of Roman Empire, as there were crowded citizens, they had no chance to hold direct democracy as Athens. In Rome, they had to act as representative system and that kind of democratic system is called **Republic**. Today, all democratic systems are Republic. In Rome, the important power of legislation was owned by the general assembly, and at the top there were two consuls who had equal power, between the two consuls and general assembly there was senate.

After the American Revolution, the American citizens held a constitutional democratic government system firstly in the world. After that, all the European countries followed and formed the **constitutional government** in their nations.

In England, after puritan revolution which was the revolution of power struggle between the king and parliament, the constitutional monarchic democracy had been formed. In that power struggle, the parliament won and seized the legislative power and they formed the new democratic system called "**Constitutional Monarchy**" in the history. Today, there are many constitutional monarchy systems in the world such as Thailand, Japan, and other Arabs, African world.

In Myanmar, after the freedom of British Colonialism, Parliamentary Democracy had been established. But because of the conflicts and antagonisms of political parties, the army seized the state power and ruled by military government at least over 6 decades. Now, after the fall down of military government, Myanmar is also operating the democratic system with three kinds of *Hluttaws* of people representatives.

The *Rajadhammasangaha*, doctrine of the Yaw Atwinwun U Bo Hlaing, is based on the seven rules of *aparihaniya* held by the Licchavi princes in the life-time of Lord Buddha. It can be found that *Rajadhammasangaha* has so many of democratic elements. So, it is suggested that they may contribute in implementation of democracy in Myanmar.

Conclusion

The aim of The *Rajadhammasangaha* doctrine is to teach and give guidelines to King Thibaw in order to govern the country with fair and justice, and to be obligated by the people. It is because the king is very young and had no experiences in politics and he had only religious knowledge of the Buddhism. This *Rajadhammasangaha* is based on the seven rules of *aparihaniya* held by the Licchavi princes in the life-time of Lord Buddha.

By holding those rules of *aparihaniya* especially the rules of consultation in a body (conference for exchange of information and advice), acting by consensus, and the law to be firmly maintained the princes could keep their country in safe and sound. So, though their Licchavi country was small when compared with country of King Ajitasatru, the King Ajitasatru could not effort to capture the Licchavi in many times and with many-added worriers and weapons. Therefore, Ananda approached the Buddha and asked why it was so. The Buddha replied that it was because of holding the seven rules of *aparihaniya* which guard its country and people. When king Ajitasatru knew about it, he made a secret plan with the

help of his close adviser and destroyed the holding of Licchavi princes' seven rules of *aparihaniya*. Then, he could challenge the princess easily.

The minister with good motive wrote his doctrine and he hoped that by appreciating the values of the seven rules of *aparihaniya* the new young King Thibaw was able to rule the country well. Besides, the king could avoid the dangerous disturbances of the queens and others around him. But, the minister missed his hope because he was lower down his rank and status after he had written that *Rajadhammasangaha*.

It has already studied that *Rajadhammasangaha* is full of democratic characters and the Licchavi princes could successfully govern their country in safe and sound though the young King Thibaw disliked it.

The practice of *Rajadhammasangaha* is the necessity for the implementation of Myanmar Democracy. It can make Myanmar Democracy transition to be smooth. *Rajadhammasangaha* is full of democratic characters. The Licchavi princes could successfully govern their country in safe and sound in a long period of years by their ruling system, which is founded on democracy. The essence of *Rajadhammasangaha* mostly represents the democratic conception. They are: majority rule, minority and individual rights, equality of opportunity, equality under the law, and civil rights and liberties, separation of power, judicial review and other checks and balances. By following the guidelines of *Rajadhammasangaha*, Myanmar Democracy transition and the relationship between the government and people can be made to be good and smooth. *Rajadhammasangaha* will guide the Myanmar People who walk on the way to the Democracy.

References

George H. Sabine. (1961). *History of Political Thought*. London: Lowe & Brydone Ltd.

Maung Htin. (2004). (L. E. Bagshawe (trans)). *Rajadhammasangaha*. New York: Grove Press.

မောင်ထင်။ (၂၀၀၂)။ *ယောမင်းကြီး ဦးစိုးလှိုင် အတ္ထုပ္ပတ္တိနှင့် ရာဇဓမ္မသင်္ဂဟကျမ်း*။ ရန်ကုန်မြို့။ ချစ်စရာစာပေ ပုံနှိပ်တိုက်။ ရန်ကုန်မြို့။